

Poisson Distribution to Gaussian and Information?

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It is well known (1) that the Poisson distribution: $P(n) = \frac{b^n \exp(-b)}{n!}$ tends to a Gaussian under two approximations. The first is Stirling's approximation in the form: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n$ and the second is that one may write $n = x + b$ and expand in powers of x , retaining an expression to $O(x^2)$. One then obtains: $\exp(-x^2/(2b))$. The mean and variance of the original Poisson distribution are b and so the new distribution (arising from a power expansion in x dealing with powers only up to x^2) yields the same variance. The mean is built in through $x = n - b$.

In general, expanding a distribution in powers of x and focusing only on the first two powers leads to a completely different distribution. To say that an expansion to second order is relevant seems to imply that both the mean and variance of the original distribution should be retained. Otherwise, there seems to be no justification to stop at x^2 . The question then becomes: If one has a distribution in the variable $x = n - b$ (where b is the average) and insists on x being very small and yet retaining the variance, one expects a symmetric rather sharp symmetric peak (as we will try to show). A symmetric peak means that one cannot have any linear term in x (otherwise x and $-x$ break symmetry about the mean) and so only the second power of x remains. Thus, it seems that this is an informational problem. One has the two constraints: $\sum_i p(x) = 1$ and $\sum_i x p(x) = b$. If one considers a minimal information function based on such constraints which only reflects the information contained in the differentials of these constraints, then one obtains the same Gaussian. Thus, we suggest there is a direct connection between the x power result of the Poisson distribution and the Gaussian achieved by maximizing entropy subject to an x^2 constraint.

Poisson Distribution

The Poisson distribution is given as: $P(n) = \frac{b^n \exp(-b)}{n!}$ ((1))

$E(n) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n \frac{b^n \exp(-b)}{n!} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b \frac{b^{n-1} \exp(-b)}{(n-1)!} = b$ ((2))

$(b^{-2}) E(n^2 - n) = \exp(-b) \frac{d}{db} \frac{d}{db} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b^n}{n!} = 1$ so

$E(n^2) - b = b^2 \rightarrow E(n^2) - E(n)E(n) = b^2 + b - b^2 = b$ ((3))

Finally, writing the variable $n - b = x$: $E(x^2) = E(n^2) - b^2 = b$ ((4))

Poisson Distribution in Certain Limits

We now follow (1) and consider the Poisson distribution under two limiting conditions. The first is to consider $n \gg 1$ and write $n!$ in terms of Stirling's approximation:

$\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n) - n$ ((5))

This is a standard approximation that is often used when factorials appear. The second approximation is more interesting, we argue. One first defines the variable:

$$x = n - b \quad ((6))$$

and assumes that it is very small so that one may perform a power series expansion in x . The idea is then to consider only the first two orders in x .

We argue that such a procedure would in general change the distribution into a completely different one unless for some reason the tiny x region about $x=0$ has the same variance of the original Poisson distribution. We have already seen from ((4)) that $E(xx) = b$, but this must be enforced also for the x expansion which now represents a different distribution.

If one consider $x=0$ and x is very tiny, but should still represent the mean and variance of the Poisson distribution, then:

$$E1(x) = E1(n-b) = 0 \quad ((6)) \quad \text{Here } E1 \text{ represents an expectation with respect to the new distribution.}$$

For x tiny, ((6)) implies equal probabilities about $x=0$ which means that the x expansion of the Poisson distribution should be an even function in x and should reproduce the same variance b (Poisson variance). As ((4)) shows, this is the value of $E(xx)$. If one has an even function, then one cannot have a linear x term in a power expansion, but only a xx term. Given that all terms may be written to the power of e , i.e.

$$B \text{ power } n = \exp(n \ln(b)) \quad \text{and} \quad 1/n! = \exp(-\ln(n) + n),$$

this xx must appear in the argument of \exp . Furthermore, one must have a drop-off with xx increasing in order to obtain a variance in a small region. This leads to a Gaussian. In other words, one may anticipate the result based on information, if in fact the second order expansion in x really matches the Poisson distribution mean and variance.

As a result, we argue that even before performing the x power expansion of the Poisson distribution, if this expansion is to have any meaning (i.e. retain mean b and variance b), then one seems to have a problem in which one is enforcing a mean b and variance b . Given that one uses the variable $n-b=x$, one does not have to worry about the mean $x=0$, but only fix the expectation of xx under this new distribution (the x expansion of the Poisson distribution).

If this is the only condition required, one might expect a maximization of entropy subject to the two constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } x \text{ } p_{\text{expand}}(x) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } x \text{ } xx \text{ } p_{\text{expand}}(x) = b \quad ((7))$$

Using: $dG=0 = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$ and $G = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(x_i) h(p(x_i))$ with

$$h(p(x_i)) = -xx/2b \quad \text{then:} \quad p(x_i) \frac{dh}{dp(x_i)} = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad p(x_i) = C \exp(-xx/(2b)) \quad ((8))$$

In other words, one may anticipate the Gaussian form based on the idea of minimal information (i.e. all information is the knowledge of the expectation of xx). The mean b is already incorporated in $x=n-b$. The Gaussian, however, is a special result because it represents the minimal information distribution. It seems that no other information other than the two constraints is required.

To see that the Poisson distribution leads to this minimal information case, one may perform the x expansion as outlined in (1), i.e.

$\ln(p(n)) = -n \ln(n) + n + n \ln(b) + b$ ((9)) from the Poisson distribution

Replacing n with $x+b$ and expanding in powers of x to second order, one has:

$\ln(p) = b + (b+x)\ln(b) + b+x - (b+x)\{\ln b + \ln(1+x/b) = b - xx/(2b) \text{ or } p = C \exp(-xx/(2b))$ ((10))

The mean is 0, so $x=n-b$ means n average $=b$ and the variance is b which retains the Poisson values, but one has a minimal information result as argued above.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is well known that a Poisson distribution can lead to a Gaussian under certain limits. These limits include letting n become large and $x= n-b$ become very small, such that a power expansion to second order in x is considered meaningful. Normally, a full expansion to all powers would be required, but if x is tiny, it is fine to consider expanding to xx , but then one would not expect the Poisson mean and variance to be maintained. We argue that if the Poisson mean and variance are to be retained in this small distance, then one must have a new distribution which is symmetric about $x=0$ and this means that it can only contain xx (if one stops the expansion at xx). Given that all terms of the Poisson expression may be written to the power of \exp , this xx (or $-xx$ actually) appears as $\exp(-\text{constant } xx)$. The key then is that this constant is $1/ (2b)$, otherwise $1/ (2 \text{ variance})$ does not match the original Poisson distribution.

We suggest that this problem is in the same form of seeking a distribution which retains the variance b in the form of $E1(xx) = b$ where $x=n-b$ and $E1$ is taken with respect to the power expansion in x (to xx) distribution. A minimum information result is the Gaussian. From $E1(x)=0$ and small x spread, one must have an even new distribution and if one expands only to xx and has $\exp(\text{function}(x))$, one must have a Gaussian. The variance constraint comes from the desire to have the new distribution have the same variance as the Poisson distribution. If it does not, one may argue that one should expand in higher powers of x than simply xx , we argue.

References

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OgT1yBI7I4Y>